

Social

HOMOPHONICS - A WORD OR NOT

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Abstract

Languages were studied. The author gathered information about different history of languages. This is an extension to homophones. Similarity or difference of pronunciation of letters, syllables, words, numbers, numerals, characters, symbols, signs, ... were discussed. Each has an origin and its pronunciation greatly matters in communication. Examples are given to show homophonics.

Keywords: Etymology; Homophonic; Languages; Loan words; Pronunciation.

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1. Introduction

While phonetics is a branch of linguistics that comprises the study of the sounds of human speech, or—in the case of sign languages—the equivalent aspects of sign (definition Lass 1998 and Carr 2003) and philology is the study of language in written historical sources; it is a combination of literary studies, history and linguistics (definition Peile 1880), homophonics comes from homophonic which means having the same sound and adding the letter s in the end to convey a subject. This pertains to the similarity or difference of pronunciations of letters, syllables, words, numbers, numerals, characters, symbols, signs, ... of a same language or different languages.

2. Methodology

Analysis was made.

Letters

A is differently pronounced in English and Tagalog, old Philippine language.
ey in English and a in Tagalog

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. .
.

Words

Transliteration - Some words are transliteration.

Misspelled words - Some words are misspelled.
Prolonged words - Some spellings of words suggest emotions.
Shortened form of words (informal) - Some words are spelled differently.
They are spelled according to what was heard.
They are words that won't be typically found in a dictionary.

Transliteration

Ex. Lalaki or lalake (Filipino words for man)

Misspelled words

Ex. Pneumatic – numatic

Note that some misspellings are worse than others.

Prolonged words

Ex. HHHHHHHHHHEEEEEEEEEELLLLLLLLLPPPPPPPP - help

Shortened form of words (informal)

Ex. Str8 - straight

3. Results

One letter not homophonic and four homophonic examples are produced.

4. Conclusion

Letters, syllables, words, numbers, numerals, characters, symbols, signs, ... are either considered as original or borrowed. In the vastness of languages, history plays an important role in their development. In pronunciation of letters, syllables, words, numbers, numerals, characters, symbols, signs, ... will only be homophonic or not. Factors that may be considered in homophonics are pronunciation, phonetics, philology, language translation, literal translation, transcription, transliteration and accent. For words, four type of words are considered namely Transliteration, Misspelled words, Prolonged words and Shortened form of words (informal).

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